

Recommended citation: Caratozzolo, P., & Membrillo-Hernández, J. (2021). Challenge Based Learning Approaches for Education 4.0 in Engineering. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 110-118). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14646956.

CHALLENGE BASED LEARNING APPROACHES FOR EDUCATION 4.0 IN ENGINEERING

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Conference Key Areas: *Challenge based education, Maker projects*

Keywords: *Educational Innovation, higher education, innovation and creativity, critical thinking, blended learning*

ABSTRACT

Higher Education Institutions in the field of engineering are currently in the process of designing teaching-learning approaches within the framework of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, Education 4.0. This process implies the need to improve the cognitive abilities of Generation Z students with regard to active, collaborative learning and personalized and self-paced teaching. Our institution had implemented in August 2019 a new educational model, based on four fundamental pillars: Challenge Based Learning (CBL), flexibility, inspiring trained teachers and, a comprehensive educational and memorable experience. The present work is a study on the effectiveness of the CBL approach in engineering; the didactic use of technological tools and the design of innovative strategies to enhance the development of the skills declared in the Education 4.0 Framework: global citizenship, innovation and creativity, technological mastery and interpersonal awareness. The methodology used was quantitative-experimental, involved more than 250 students and was developed over three years. The use of several assessment instruments allowed to obtain conclusive results: (i) the impact of the design and implementation of adequate cognitive tools on the quality of learning outcomes; and (ii) the relevance of the use of cutting-edge technological tools in each stage of a 2D learning taxonomy (cognitive process dimension / knowledge dimension).

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1 INTRODUCTION

Education 4.0 is an educational approach designed to align with the emerging fourth industrial revolution. The pillars of this new industrial revolution are intelligent technology, artificial intelligence and robotics, Biotechnology and Sustainability. It must contain a more real approach, more of the current environment, real issues, real answers [1]. Universities have had to change their teaching-learning models to focus on these areas of study. However, this would not be enough, but the students must learn about the areas by doing, that is, under a practical, dynamic scheme, changing the knowledge transfer approach in a way that is closer to the environment in which we live today [2].

This makes engineering education go through significant changes. Therefore, it requires academics to modify traditional engineering education. Taking into account the principles of Industry 4.0, the teaching staff should allow their students to face Industry 4.0 and to continue researching on the subject in conditions of lifelong learning. In other words, it requires establishing tangible engineering competencies in both processing and thinking that can be applied to emerging technologies [3].

In addition, education needs new adaptable education systems that are developed and realized through the use of technology and the Internet, more in events such as the COVID-19 pandemic [4]. Technology-enhanced learning offers such possibilities by supporting the teaching and learning process through the integration of e-learning and technology. Provides access to socio-technical innovations. Learning with technology can maximize students' academic experience in fast-growing areas of interest to Industry 4.0 at all levels of global education. This requires strategies such as challenge-based learning or active learning. There is a gap that is created between the need for employers to certify that students possess the skills required for the work environment and the current circumstances of the pandemic that prevent educators from fully developing these skills. Therefore, the study and proposal of new strategies of the teaching-learning procedure that decrease this gap are extremely necessary. Education in the Fourth Industrial Revolution can be identified with four skills and four learning characteristics of high-quality learning, the Education 4.0 Framework, as shown in Table 1.

This study addresses the following research question on how to intellectually involve engineering students by promoting soft skills (considering technological tools and digital transformation not as goals in themselves but as means):

How to incorporate in Challenge-based settings those open learning experiences that develop Education 4.0 skills using tools from an Active Learning approach?

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Challenge-based Learning Theory

CBL has its roots in Experiential Learning (EL), which has as its fundamental principle that students learn better when they actively participate in open learning experiences than when they passively participate in structured activities. Therefore, EL provides opportunities for students to apply what they learn to real-world situations where they face problems, discover for themselves, test solutions, and interact with other students within a given context [5]. EL is an integrative and holistic learning approach that combines experience, cognition, and behavior [6].

EL approach involves much more than just participating in “doing something,” solving a problem that has been previously solved by the teacher, or getting involved in a project as an assistant. It should be noted that EL can be used in Project-Based Learning, however for the CBL, the level of uncertainty is different, mainly when there are agreements between universities and training partners where students are scholarship holders or interns at the training partner's facilities, because sometimes the experience of interactions is limited to students doing jobs with little demand and almost always challenging.

On the one hand, the first priority of the new educational model was for our university to establish agreements with the training partners in accordance with the objectives of the educational model. This, of course, implies an understanding on the part of the training partner that the main objective is the development of competencies through solving the challenges that the training partner wants to solve. On the other hand, the university undertakes to respect at all times the confidentiality of the process, the intellectual property of the resolution of the challenge, and the guidelines of both the engineering school and the training partner to understand how students can develop competencies through CBL experience [7][8].

Table 1. Skills and learning characteristics of the Education 4.0 Framework

Skills	Global citizenship Innovation and creativity Technology Interpersonal	Learning Characteristics	Personalized and self-paced Accessible and inclusive Collaborative Student-driven
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2.2 ACTIVE LEARNING THEORY

Some of the essential conditions to promote effective Active Learning (AL) experiences are [9]:

- ❖ Learning experiences should include activities of reflection, critical analysis and synthesis.
- ❖ Learning experiences should be structured in a way that promotes decision making and student responsibility for results.
- ❖ The experience must involve all participants not only intellectually but also emotionally and socially.
- ❖ The instructor and students may experience success, failure, uncertainty, and risk taking, because the results of the experience may not be entirely predictable.
- ❖ The experience should promote students' self-awareness, empathy with their peers and a greater knowledge of the environment and other cultures.

AL and CBL are educational process approaches that have been successfully incorporated into engineering curricula because they achieve a real-world perspective and view student learning as a process by "doing" on a subject of study. It is a type of experiential education where students are exposed to situations in their environment, AL is the basis of pedagogical activities and CBL is the didactic technique where the student faces a real problem where their knowledge, experience, multidisciplinary and collaborative work It is necessary to develop a proposal for a solution to the challenge. The result is obviously the development of both transversal and disciplinary competencies. These approaches offer a student-centered learning framework that emulates real work experiences in industry and

corporations: they build on student interest in giving practical meaning to education, while developing key competencies observed by organizations international: Leadership and social influence; Emotional intelligence; Reasoning; Problem solving and ideation; and Analysis and evaluation of the system.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The design chosen for the project was the Experimental Research, Quantitative, 4-group Solomon type [10]. It was intended to control the possible interaction that could exist between the PreTest and the Treatment. Two groups have received PreTest (EG-T-PreT and CG-PreT) while other two have not. Likewise, two groups have received Treatment (EG-T-PreT and EG-T) while other two have not. The group criteria were the following:

EG-T-PreT: Experimental Group, Treatment with PreTest

EG-T: Experimental Group, only Treatment without PreTest

CG-PreT: Control Group with PreTest

CG: Control Group without PreTest

The study was mainly based on the implementation of both approaches, CBL and AL, and all students participated simultaneously in activities that promote learning and enrichment of disciplinary competences, as well as transversal competences [2]. During these experiences, students were guided by the authors and supported by partners, who contribute not only to the design and implementation of activities, but also to the feedback received by teachers and students at the end of the process. The methodological design is schematically illustrated in Figure 1.

3.2 Participants

A total of different groups were involved over six semesters (S1 to S6), from August 2018 to June 2021, as shown in Table 2. The research was conducted with a sample of 330 students that joined the study voluntarily, 130 of them during 2018-2019 in face-to-face (F2F) learning settings, and other 200 of them, during 2020/2021, in fully online (OL) learning settings. The experimental group -198 students- underwent cognitive and metacognitive instruction (with Treatment), while 132 students remained untrained in the control group (without Treatment). Of the 198 experimental group students, 102 received pre-test and treatment and 96 students received only treatment. Of the 132 students in the control group, 74 received the pre-test and the remaining 58 students did not.

It is important to emphasize that the students of the 14 groups that appear in Table 2 participated in the Post-Test. Participants who contributed to this study had an average age of 22 years by the end of each semester and were distributed in nine different courses (the official ID of each program and courses appears in parentheses) taught by both authors, as follows:

B.S. Sustainable Development Engineering program (IDS):

- Biology and Sustainable Development (BT1009)
- Natural Resources Management and Climate Change (DS3002)
- Capstone Project for Sustainable Development (DS3005)
- Integration of Energy Processes (IQ2001B)
- Technologies for the Efficient use of Electricity (TE2042)

Energy Distribution Systems (TE3053)

B.S. Biotechnology Engineering program (IBT):

- Molecular Biology (BT1003)
- Biomimetics and Sustainability (IB1006)

B.S. Mechatronics Engineering program (IMT):

- Applied Electronics (TE2033)

Fig. 1. Procedure Design.

Table 2. Methodological data used in the study.

Group Type	#Group	#Students	Course	Program	Modality	Semester & Year
EG-T-PreT (102 students)	1	32	IB1006	IBT	OL	S6-2021
	2	26	IB1006	IBT	OL	S5-2020
	3	26	TE2033	IMT	OL	S6-2021
	4	18	DS3002	IDS	OL	S6-2021
	5	30	IQ2001B	IDS	OL	S6-2021
EG-T (96 students)	6	17	TE2033	IMT	F2F	S3-2019
	7	26	BT1003	IBT	F2F	S2-2019
	8	23	TE3053	IDS	F2F	S3-2019
CG-PreT (74 students)	9	29	TE2033	IMT	OL	S4-2020
	10	24	IB1006	IBT	F2F	S3-2019
	11	21	TE2042	IDS	OL	S4-2020
CG (58 students)	12	15	DS3005	IDS	F2F	S1-2018
	13	25	BT1003	IBT	F2F	S1-2018
	14	18	BT1009	IDS	OL	S5-2020
TOTAL students		330				

3.3 Open Active Learning Experiences (Treatment)

The best strategy for the incorporation of the open learning experiences was in the form of didactic interventions and integrated infusion-immersion approach in curricular courses of the engineering programs [11][12]. The activities were designed

considering the actual cognitive stages of thinking of the students, and incorporated analysis sessions. The treatment included some of the following experiences (competences/skills to develop appear in parentheses):

- Dialogue Seminars, held after hours and outside the classroom, in spaces with adequate furniture of the Learning Commons, in F2F courses, and in videoconferences rooms, in OL courses (Broad Perspective).
- Supervised Questioning Session with a leader instructor to stimulate the recall of knowledge and sharpen understanding of concepts acquired in previous sessions (Criticality)
- Challenge-based learning with experts in industry facilities, energy utilities facilities and technology companies (Teamwork).
- Training of students in the operation of the cockpit console of the radio station, training in the use and production of audio with portable equipment for recording podcasts in the classroom and outdoors (Transfer).
- Student participation in contests and competitions of cultural nature (Creativity and Taking Risks)

3.4 Instrumentation (Data Collection in Pre-Test and Post-Test)

Diverse types of instruments were used: diagnostic tests, with multiple-choice and true or false questions designed to establish the approximate knowledge of each student; Reading comprehension tests, designed to determine the level of cognitive maturity of students; a modified version of the tests and rubrics presented by Paul & Elder; and finally, to assess how well students performed each outcome and considering that assessing the evidence for competences and soft skills involves subjective judgments concerning products or behaviors, an already-existing rubric was used, the VALUE Rubrics, from AAC&U, developed for the Essential Learning Outcomes of the Association of American Colleges and Universities [13].

PreTests were important to know the level of cognitive maturity of students. In this study, Egan's taxonomy was used to place students on the different five levels. It is important to emphasize that the PreTest does not have a diagnostic function in terms of domain-specific knowledge level. The PreTest were also used to know the level of development that students have in Education 4.0 skills.

4 RESULTS, FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

During the first three semesters of the project (S1, S2, S3), preliminary treatments were conducted on 66 students to determine with greater accuracy the flexibility and design of the assessment tools, while 64 students were included in the control group. In the spring semester of 2020 (S4), the emergence of COVID-19 forced us to abruptly to modify our design to go from face-to-face learning to online learning through the ZOOM platform; we adapt the collaborative sessions to be carried out in videoconference format and the laboratory sessions to be carried out, some in simulation software and others in remote laboratory systems. In that semester 50 students of the control group performed the Post-Tests. Finally, in the last two semesters of the study (S5, S6) a total of 132 students were included in the

experimental group, performing the modified and adapted treatment to be carried out 100% online; in that period 68 students participated in the control group.

In order to verify that the students of the experimental group and the control group had similar initial conditions of soft skills development, the results of diagnostic pre-tests in both groups were compared. Initial comparison between 176 students (102 students of the EG-T-PreT and 74 of the CG-PreT), revealed no significant differences in their skills background, as shown in Figure 2a. The finding of relevance that we can report from the pre-tests is the strong impact of social-emotional skills, noted in students in semesters S5 and S6 (from August 2020 to June 2021), presumably due to disappointment and frustration when starting a semester under strict measures of confinement and social distancing caused by the second wave of COVID-19.

The preliminary analysis of the results obtained in the Post-Tests of the years 2018-2019 revealed that the situation attended in the teaching-learning involved the insecurity in effective communication (oral and written) and the difficulty in developing soft skills and transversal competences. The post-tests on digital skills using VALUE rubrics showed that the experimental group attained 37% improvement over the students of the control group in the upper "Capstone" level and a 35% decrease in the number of students at the lowest "Benchmark" level of the rubric, , as shown in Figure 2b. The exercise of activities in small groups was highly beneficial, so that our methodology can be considered a successful, especially in fully online environments.

The results showed that the Open Active Learning Experiences established a positive effect, since it could be verified that the work of heterogeneous active groups also favours different affective results, as self-motivation, personal ethics, enthusiasm, and intellectual responsibility.

Figure 2.a) Pre-test Performance in semesters S3, S4, S5 and S6. b) CG vs. EG Post-Test Performance.

Faced with the triggering question, regarding how to insert Active Learning experiences in CBL courses, our proposal to use technology-enhanced open experiences was a viable option, since the students themselves recognize -in both

academic course and training exit surveys- a significant increase in the Education 4.0 Framework skills, as well as in socio-emotional empathy.

The adoption of open learning spaces made it difficult to predict how students would respond to the contributions of their peers, how the interthinking process would evolve and to what extent each would develop the Education 4.0 framework skills. Challenge-based learning approach also involved the instructor making decision was a process with the necessary flexibility to change the instructional process in midstream. In addition, those environments demanded a high degree of leadership on the part of the instructor and a strong emerging collaboration between instructor-student and between students with their peers.

Although a broader distribution was intended, only the students who were interested in participating in the study could be included in the sample. Because of this, the groups of students from the engineering program in which we are associated are not completely representative of higher education in our institution.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

During the last year, due to the emergence of the COVID-19 crisis, all higher education institutions adapted their curricular courses to partially known digital and technological environments, and revisited the syllabi to be taught in completely online courses. The challenge was enormous, and differences of opinion persisted on how to include advanced technological tools virtually in the courses to achieve a good development for the soft skills of the Education 4.0 framework. The present work is a study on the effectiveness of Active and Challenge-based Learning Approaches and the didactic use of some technological tools. The design of innovative strategies made it possible to enhance the development of some of the required skills such as: global citizenship, innovation and creativity, digital literacy and interpersonal awareness. The use of rubrics allowed to obtain conclusive results since it revealed the importance of promoting the formation of metacognitive awareness, and the great impact of the design and implementation of adequate cognitive tools to achieve high quality results in the learning process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial and the technical support of Writing Lab, Institute for the Future of Education, Tecnológico de Monterrey, in the production of this work. The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of Novus Grant with PEP no. PHHT090-19ZZ00008, Institute for the Future of Education, Tecnológico de Monterrey, in the production of this work.

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